

Figure 1 - Animated gif showing Hurricane Nicole Prediction; credit: windy.com

MESS 0039

MET 2.31 - Proof that the Mainstream Meteorologists [and their particular form of Change Theory¹ created through Machine-Learning + Data Analytics (DAML)] are finding the same results we do in Electrometeorology (EGM) [part 2]

Sf. R. Careaga, BSEE, MSTOM
January 2023

Best Viewed at: <http://bit.ly/40ciMaX>

ABSTRACT

In this paper, we continue the model through the predictive phase, and then examine the actual precipitation data in the Pine Mountain Flux region. There is A+ (gold) evidence presented here of the EGM model; which leads nicely into the third part, where A++ (platinum) evidence is presented on EGM theory involving the New Madrid Zone and the Knobs Region.

Keywords: Hurricane Nicole - precipitation - Pine Mountain - Kentucky

¹ [MIMS - Applying Change Theory](#)

Recollection

In MESS 0038, the author examined the live data surrounding the November 2022 Hurricane Nicole, and its obvious connections (EGM) to an Earthspot over the Ogallala (High Plains) water table - a Nor'wester - which had a massive temperature drop, and humidity polarization. Interestingly enough - and important for this paper - is that there was **no cloud coverage over the New Madrid Fault Zone^{2 3} and Pine Mountain karst area at the time**. In fact, in the Bluegrass state, in its entirety, was clear blue skies, and it was a “yang” day, but with confused energetics, on account of the motion of the air at the time.

Figure 2 - Actual Precipitation results for 11 AM, Friday November 11, 2022; credit: windy.com

It is important to understand the premise here. The Change Theory models used for mainstream meteorology relies upon data analytics and machine learning algorithms. These predictive models are running themselves, with some guidance of the Standard Model of meteorology. However, mostly, all the MET science these days runs on new models that can actually show how wrong previous models are, because of actual air mass and temperature/pressure data entering the model. In fact, they can, with a great degree of accuracy, discuss actual electrical power in tornados, etc. With this in mind, keep a realization that the actual rain values

² [MESS0019: MET 2.1 - KY Tornado New Madrid Zone & magnetics](#)

³ [MESS0021: GEO 2.22 - New Madrid Zone and Blue Ridge: Magmaflux](#)

will vary from predictions - and this is what matters. The DAML used makes its predictions based upon past data, and accurate representations, which show the EGM regions so very clearly. (see Figure 3)

Figure 3 - Windy App prediction for 10 am Friday, made Wednesday, Nov. 9, 2022

Regions (white letters) added by author

- Knobs Region - best known EGM Lichtenberg with EMP on professional drone recorded⁴
- Big South Fork - gravity anomaly⁵
- Daniel Boone National Forest leyline - known EGM region of arches, waterfalls, sandstone, etc. with A+ evidence for anti-stratigraphy at the Dogfoot Hollow wall⁶, and Pebble Beach wall⁷ in Red River Gorge wildlife preserve and state park.
- Pine Mountain karst formation, also sandstone; with A+ evidence of Yelverton-Hall Crooked Smile Keystone (CSK)⁸

*Note that it is absolutely expected that the Big South Fork will have a spike in precipitation; however this spike is occurring over the “canyonlands” whose most dominant geological feature is a picture-perfect complete arch, the Natural Arch, whose counterpart is at the Natural Bridge State Resort Park, across the highway from the Red River Gorge far away in Wolfe County. The RRG area confluence with Olympia and the highlands dells (knobs) is where a large amount of history is occurring, plus the Pilot Knob of Daniel Boone, and is where the most precipitation in the state occurs (north of the Pine Mountain and Black Mountain/Stone Mountain confluences).

**Note also the DAML is predicting more intense rainfall at the BSF than even at the Smokey Mountain National Park. It knows the anomaly there, even if only by macrolytic evidence.

⁴ A- evidence: [Trip Report: Culvertown Platform Addendum](#)

⁵ A evidence: [MESS0018: GEO 2.2 - Magnetic Anomalies in VA and KY](#)

⁶ A evidence: [AKHA Newsletter November, 2018](#)

⁷ A+ evidence: [Trip Report: Pebble Beach, Red River Gorge](#)

⁸ A+ evidence: [MESS0020: GEO 2.21 - Andy Hall's Crooked Smile Hypothesis Proven by the Pine Mountain flux](#)

Figure 4 - cloud coverage Friday 11 am-1 pm, showing where the storm actually progressed (and to what intensity). It turned out the greatest intensity was NOT at the Big South Fork, but at the Tennessee CSK 90-degree “Jellico Bend”, where the magnetic escarpment is taking place; and at Nantahala in North Carolina. There is also a concentration ahead of the DBNF leyline, along the “Cumberland” vector through the knobs region proper, up into the peak of the dolomite dome at Lexington. There is, if anything, a dearth of intensity at the Wildcat Mountain anomaly. However, the Red Bird NF anomaly appears active.

Figure 5 (next page) - Pine Mountain karst area showing **clear** transmutation relevance, that matches the electronic-discharge machining (EDM) of the Pennyroyal area, but *impossibly* does not extend to the north or south of the Pine Mountain flux. This is A++ evidence *when combined with* the CSK evidence, which is based on empirical lab data. Credit: KY geological survey

* Please note the sharp difference in the leading edge of the Eastern Pennyroyal karst area with the Big South Fork and DBNF leyline; which is presumably of a more ancient (ie, Denosovian) genesis formation.

** Note also the connection of the Western Pennyroyal arc to the flourspar/Hicks Dome (Garden of the Gods)/Land Between the Lakes EGM features. Also between the two Pennyroyal karst regions, the knobs Lichtenberg and arc exists. This may be our first strong evidence for other than electron and proton charge formation methods, or at least that there is probably a difference of ground-to-object or object-to-ground discharge, as well of course as voltage and current MAGNITUDE.

Conclusion

The first two parts form an important present+future (the predictive aspect of hypothesis in the scientific method) hammer and anvil. However, it is the third part which provides the strongest evidence yet, outside of the facts provided at Garden of the Gods and Shiprock⁹ of visual and sample proof of non-SM explanations, that EGM hypothesis is correct. What's important here in this paper is that the DAML modeling used by the windy app (based on NOAA) and website are seeing what electrogeologists are seeing and predicting. This paper did an excellent job of building the continual visual evidence for the regions thus far examined, and constitutes gold-level evidence.

⁹ Trip Report: Shiprock and Barringer Crater

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